

Research article

Myriochila (Myriochila) melancholica melancholica (Fabricius, 1798) (Coleoptera, Cicindelidae), an expectable addition to the Bulgarian fauna

Fabian A. Boetzl¹, Lara Burtchen², Teodora M. Teofilova³

- (1) [Corresponding author] Department of Animal Ecology and Tropical Biology, Biocenter, University of Würzburg, Am Hubland, 97074 Würzburg, Germany, fabian.boetzl@uni-wuerzburg.de
- (2) Department of Animal Ecology and Tropical Biology, Biocenter, University of Würzburg, Am Hubland, 97074 Würzburg, Germany, lara.burtchen@stud-mail.uni-wuerzburg.de
- (3) Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research (IBER), Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (BAS), 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, oberon_zoo@abv.bg

Abstract: The wide-spread tiger beetle species *Myriochila (Myriochila) melancholica* (Fabricius, 1798) (Coleoptera, Cicindelidae) is recorded for the first time for the territory of Bulgaria. It was collected from the Struma River Valley, a dispersal corridor for many Mediterranean and thermophilic species. We also comment on the distribution and ecology of the species.

Keywords: Bulgaria, new records, regional studies, species distribution, tiger beetles

Introduction

The Mediterranean region and especially the southern Balkan Peninsula are a hotspot of tiger beetle diversity in Europe (Jaskuła, 2015; Jaskuła et al., 2019). Despite the popularity of tiger beetles among collectors, new taxa are still regularly described from this region (López & Dementyev, 2017; Boetzl & Franzen, 2020; Sparacio et al., 2023) and their taxonomy is perpetually being revised (Assmann et al., 2018; Romano & Sparacio, 2018; Gebert et al., 2021). In addition, climate change is shifting the distribution ranges of species northward (Parmesan et al., 1999; Drees et al., 2011). New records of tiger beetles for many European countries adjacent to or within the Mediterranean region can thus be expected.

Among all known tiger beetle species, *Myriochila (Myriochila) melancholica* (Fabricius, 1798) has the most extensive distribution range: The species occurs from the Mediterranean over the Middle East and Central Asia (including Xinjiang Province in China) to the Indian subcontinent and across all of Africa except Madagascar (Putchkov & Matalin, 2017;

Wiesner, 2020) (Fig. 1). Apart from the nominate subspecies that is distributed throughout most of the range of the species, only one subspecies, *Myriochila (Myriochila) melancholica semicircumcincta* (Mandl, 1959), is currently known from southern Iran (Mandl, 1959). In the Mediterranean region, the species was previously known from the Maghreb (Algeria, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia), Egypt, the Levant (Israel, Lebanon, Palestine, Syria), Cyprus, Turkey, Greece, Albania, Italy, (southern) France, Spain, and Portugal (Fig. 1). *Myriochila melancholica* currently reaches its northernmost distribution limit in Europe in the Ardèche mountain range in southern France and the Northern Greek lowlands (Fig. 1).

Myriochila melancholica is a species commonly encountered on sparsely vegetated and muddy microhabitats along the shores of stagnant and flowing waterbodies but also on moist dirt roads and in salt marshes (Cassola, 1999; Abdel-Dayem et al., 2003; Franzen, 2006; Jaskuła & Rewicz, 2015; Assmann et al., 2018). The species is clearly bound to moist habitats and often inhabits temporary microhabitats of the dynamic alluvial systems of naturally flowing rivers

Fig. 1. Distribution range of *Myriochila melancholica* in Africa and Eurasia, with countries with known occurrence highlighted in green (data according to the current Checklist of the tiger beetles of the world (Wiesner, 2020) and Bulgaria highlighted in purple. Black dots represent individual observations obtained from GBIF (GBIF.org, 2025) and from a private database of verified collection material and literature records. These known locations are displayed to visualise distributions within countries and are not representative for the overall distribution as they mostly indicate accessible locations with a high density of entomologists or of entomological interest. The habitus image on the bottom right was taken by the first author in May 2022 in Greece.

which forces populations to be mobile (Franzen, 2006). While *M. melancholica* was known from Northern Greece (Franzen, 2011), it had so far not been recorded from Bulgaria.

Materials and methods

A single, male specimen of *M. melancholica melancholica* (Fig. 2A) was collected on 4 August 2025 around noon using a sweep net (clear sky, no wind, ~ 34 °C) on a gravel bank on the right side of the Struma River (approximately 145 m above the sea level) near Rupite Site and Kozhuh Mountain (41.457194N 23.271500E; Blagoevgrad Province, Bulgaria; Fig. 2B). The individual was active on a moist and muddy section of the gravel bank close to the waterline in bright sunlight (Fig. 2C). The species occurred together with several individuals of another tiger beetle species, *Calomera fischeri fischeri* (M.F. Adams, 1817), that preferred gravel-dominated

sections of the bank. The specimen was identified by the first author and is deposited in his working collection (cFB, Würzburg, Germany).

Maps were produced using QGIS (version 3.40.6; Graser et al., 2025), additional distribution data displayed in Fig. 1 was downloaded from GBIF and cleaned (GBIF.org, 2025) and supplemented with distribution data held in a private database of collection material made available to the first author. The specimen photo was generated from an image stack taken using a Canon EOS R7 with the MP-E 65mm f/2.8 1-5x macro lens on a copy stand.

Results and discussion

The discovery of *M. melancholica* raises the total number of ground beetle (Carabidae) and tiger beetle (Cicindelidae) species in Bulgaria to 758 and the number of tiger beetle species currently found in Bulgaria to 15 (16, if we count *Cephalota turcica*

Fig. 2. Habitus of the male specimen of *Myriochila (Myriochila) melancholica melancholica* (Fabricius, 1798) collected near Rupite (A, scale bar: 5 mm), the collection location within Bulgaria (B) and a picture of the habitat on the collection day (C).

(Schaum, 1859) as only one male of this species was ever found in Bulgaria in 1918 (Guéorguiev, 2004; Franzen, 2011). While *M. melancholica* was known from Northern Greece (Franzen, 2011), including the Struma/Strymonas estuary region (Fig. 1) it was so far absent from Bulgaria despite the presence of suitable habitats along the Struma River (see Fig. 2C). Such suitable habitats exist in many locations along the Struma and Mesta rivers and further, undiscovered populations of *M. melancholica* in suitable microhabitats can be expected.

Franzen (2006) observed *M. melancholica* on the Greek Peloponnese often in single individuals and speculated that the species is likely a good and active disperser that can quickly colonise the preferred transient microhabitats in dynamic alluvial systems.

The species is indeed often found attracted to light sources at night (Abdel-Dayem et al., 2003; Assmann et al., 2018) and a common bycatch in moth traps (personal observation) which indicates a good dispersal potential. That the species does not form distinct subspecies across its huge range (apart from one found in southern Iran) is further evidence for dispersal connecting even distant populations. We believe it is likely that the sole individual encountered in a suitable microhabitat on the gravel bank near Rupite Site and the emblematic refugium of Kozhuh Mountain was a disperser, likely originating from the known populations in northern Greece. Further records in the future are needed to verify that the species has indeed permanently established in Bulgaria.

The discovery of *M. melancholica* in Bulgaria results in a northward shift of the known distribution range on the southern Balkan Peninsula. The species was previously only found south of the Belasitsa/Kerkini and Sharliya/Vrontous mountain ranges. While it seems plausible that this warm-adapted species might have moved northward as a result of warming climate and recent drought spells in southern Bulgaria using the Struma Valley as a dispersal axis, it is also possible that it was simply overlooked in previous assessments (Hieke & Wrase, 1988; Guéorguiev & Guéorguiev, 1995). Many regions of Bulgaria are indeed poorly assessed and several new carabid beetle species have been detected in recent years that likely had been present previously but remained undetected (Teofilova, 2024; Teofilova & Boetzl, 2024; Teofilova et al., 2025). Especially the understudied and biodiverse mountainous regions in the southwest of Bulgaria and the Struma and Mesta valleys as potential dispersal axes for northward expanding Mediterranean species deserve further attention by entomologists. It seems likely that more additions to the Bulgarian fauna will be discovered there in the future.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to Jörg Gebert (Dresden, Germany) for providing additional distribution records of *M. melancholica* displayed in Fig. 1, to Jochen Krauss (University of Würzburg, Germany) for organising the field trip to Bulgaria during which the specimen was collected and to Stilian Stefanov (Haskovo, Bulgaria) for his expertise and company during the field trip.

Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the author, reviewers, or subject editor.

Author' contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Fabian A. Boetzl: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, project administration, visualisation, writing—original draft; Lara Burtchen:

investigation, validation, writing—review and editing; Teodora Teofilova: validation, visualisation, writing—review and editing.

References

- Abdel-Dayem M.S., El-Hawagry M.S., Hassan S.A. 2003 A review of the Egyptian species of tiger beetles (Coleoptera, Carabidae, Cicindelinae). *Bulletin of the entomological society of Egypt* 80: 193–217.
- Assmann T., Boutaud E., Buse J., Gebert J., Drees C., Friedman A.L.L., Khoury F., Marcus T., Orbach E., Renan I., Schmidt C., Zumstein P. 2018 The tiger beetles (Coleoptera, Cicindelidae) of the southern Levant and adjacent territories: from cybertaxonomy to conservation biology. *ZooKeys* 734: 43–103.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.734.21989>
- Boetzl F.A., Franzen M. 2020 Taxonomy and distribution of *Cylindera germanica* (Linnaeus, 1758) in the Middle East with the description of two new subspecies (Coleoptera, Carabidae, Cicindelinae). *Zootaxa* 4809 (1): 95–110.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4809.1.5>
- Cassola F. 1999 Studies on tiger beetles. CVII. The cicindelid fauna of Anatolia: faunistics and biogeography (Coleoptera, Cicindelidae). *Biogeographia* 20: 229–276.
<https://doi.org/10.21426/B6110089>
- Drees C., Brandmayr P., Buse J., Dieker P., Gürlich S., Habel J., Harry I., Hardtle W., Matern A., Meyer H., Pizzoloto R., Quante M., Shafer K., Schuldt A., Taboada Palomares A., Assmann T. 2011 Poleward range expansion without a southern contraction in the ground beetle *Agonum viridicupreum* (Coleoptera, Carabidae). *ZooKeys* 100: 333–352.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.100.1535>
- Franzen M. 2006 Verbreitung und Lebensräume der Sandlaufkäfer der Peloponnes-Halbinsel, Griechenland (Coleoptera, Cicindelidae). *Nachrichtenblatt der Bayerischen Entomologen* 55 (3/4): 46–64.
- Franzen M. 2011 *Cephalota turcica* (Schaum, 1859) – Verbreitung, Habitate und Gefährdungspotenzial einer seltenen ostmediterranen Sandlaufkäferart (Coleoptera: Cicindelidae). *Entomologische Zeitschrift* 121 (3): 133–140.

- GBIF.org 2025 Occurrence Download. The Global Biodiversity Information Facility.
<https://doi.org/10.15468/DL.EFHXAK>
- Gebert J., Matalin A.V., Boetzl F.A. 2021 Revision of the Palearctic *Cicindela campestris* species complex – Part 1: On the taxonomy, identification and ecology of *Cicindela herbacea* Klug, 1832 and *Cicindela javettii* Chaudoir, 1861 (Coleoptera, Cicindelidae). *Zootaxa* 4990 (3): 469–510.
<https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4990.3.3>
- Graser A., Sutton T., Bernasocchi M. 2025 The QGIS project: Spatial without compromise. *Patterns* 6 (7): 101265.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2025.101265>
- Guéorguiev B.V. 2004 Adepagous and some staphyliniform beetles (Insecta: Coleoptera) in the Eastern Rhodopes (Bulgaria and Greece). In: Beron P., Popov A. (eds) Biodiversity of Bulgaria. 2. Biodiversity of Eastern Rhodopes (Bulgaria and Greece). Pensoft Publishers & Nat. Mus. Natur. Hist., Sofia, 379–411.
- Guéorguiev V.B., Guéorguiev B.V. 1995 Catalogue of the ground-beetles of Bulgaria (Coleoptera: Carabidae). Pensoft Publishers, Sofia–Moscow, 279 pp.
- Hieke F., Wrase D. 1988 Faunistik der Laufkäfer Bulgariens (Coleoptera, Carabidae). *Deutsche Entomologische Zeitschrift N.F.* 35 (1-3): 1–171.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/mmnd.19880350102>
- Jaskuła R. 2015 The Maghreb – one more important biodiversity hot spot for tiger beetle fauna (Coleoptera, Carabidae, Cicindelinae) in the Mediterranean region. *ZooKeys* 482: 35–53.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.482.8831>
- Jaskuła R., Plóciennik M., Schwerk A. 2019 From climate zone to microhabitat–environmental factors affecting the coastal distribution of tiger beetles (Coleoptera: Cicindelidae) in the south-eastern European biodiversity hotspot. *PeerJ* 7: e6676.
<https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.6676>
- Jaskuła R., Rewicz T. 2015 Tiger beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae: Cicindelinae) of Tunisia: distribution, phenology, taxa list and new records. *African entomology* 23 (2): 467–485.
<https://doi.org/10.4001/003.023.0217>
- López M.A., Dementyev S. 2017 Description of *Cylindera (Cylindera) germanica lyciae* ssp. nov. from Turkey and corologic contribution on *Cylindera (Cylindera) germanica* (Linnaeus, 1758) for Spain (Coleoptera: Cicindelidae). *Boletín de la Sociedad entomológica Aragonesa (S.E.A.)* 60: 1–5.
- Mandl K. 1959 Eine Ausbeute an Cicindeliden aus Iran, Ergebnisse der Entomologischen Reisen Willi Richter, Stuttgart, im Iran 1954 und 1956 – Nr. 19. *Stuttgarter Beiträge zur Naturkunde* 18: 1–3.
- Parmesan C., Ryrholm N., Stefanescu C., Hill J.K., Thomas C.D., Descimon H., Huntley B., Kaila L., Kullberg J., Tammaru T., Tennent W.J., Thomas J.A., Warren M. 1999 Poleward shifts in geographical ranges of butterfly species associated with regional warming. *Nature* 399: 579–583.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/21181>
- Putchkov A.V., Matalin A.V. 2017 Subfamily Cicindelinae Latreille, 1802. In: Löbl I., Löbl D. (eds) Catalogue of Palearctic Coleoptera. Volume 1. Revised and Updated Edition. Archostemata – Myxophaga – Adepaga. Brill, Leiden–Boston, 217–249.
<https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004330290>
- Romano M., Sparacio I. 2018 Taxonomic and biogeographical observations on a new population of *Calomera* Motschulsky, 1862 (Coleoptera Carabidae Cicindelinae) from Crete Island (Greece). *Biodiversity Journal* 9 (3): 195–204.
<https://doi.org/10.31396/Biodiv.Jour.2018.9.3.195.204>
- Sparacio I., Lo Cascio P., Muscarella C., Surdo S., Falci A., Allegrino F. 2023 A new subspecies of *Cicindela (Cicindela) campestris* Linnaeus, 1758 (Coleoptera Cicindelidae) from the Aeolian Islands (Italy). *Biodiversity Journal* 14 (4): 741–747.
<https://doi.org/10.31396/Biodiv.Jour.2023.14.4.741.747>
- Teofilova T. 2024 A further new steppe ground beetle species for the Bulgarian fauna: *Amara (Parapercosia) taurica* (Motschulsky, 1845) (Coleoptera: Carabidae) appeared in the karst refugium of the Chepan Planina Mountain. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 76 (3): 315–322.
<https://doi.org/10.71424/azb76.3.002785>
- Teofilova T.M., Boetzl F.A. 2024 A contribution to Bulgarian ground beetle fauna (Coleoptera: Carabidae) with the first record of *Agonum carbonarium* Dejean, 1828 for the country. *Historia naturalis bulgarica* 46 (8): 215–226.
<https://doi.org/10.48027/hnb.46.082>

Fabian A. Boetzl, Lara Burtchen, Teodora M. Teofilova

Teofilova T., Rapuzzi I., Kodzhabashev N. 2025
Carabus (Tomocarabus) bessarabicus tangra
(Coleoptera: Carabidae): a new subspecies from
the karst steppe refugia of the Chepan Planina and
Tri Ushi Mountains in Central-Western Bulgaria.
Acta Zoologica Bulgarica 77 (1): 3–12.
<https://doi.org/10.71424/azb77.1.002825>

Wiesner J. 2020 Checklist of the tiger beetles of the
world. 2nd. Edition. Edition Winterwork,
Borsdorf, 540 pp.